

Reuse of low-density fibreboards for insulation use

Fibreboard is a type of engineered wood product that is made from wood fibres. Structural cohesion is essentially based on the interlacing of the wood fibers with a small amount of binder. Demand for wood fibre insulation boards is increasing to meet all requirements for building facades in multi storey, residential- and public buildings, in rural and urban areas.

Small amounts of binders and several types of additives (to improve their fire properties and water repellency) are necessary to enable use in multi-story buildings. A mixture of untreated fibers containing post-industrial and recycled wood chips and shavings, as well as wood that has been harvested and grown according to sustainable forest management practices can be used.

Regional coverage and transferability

Leading companies are today identified in Central Europe.

The practice can be transferred and manufactured in other regions where they have access to untreated wood resources including post-consumer wood.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ The use of 100% untreated recycled wood as raw material is technically possible and provides a high added value to recovered wood as a source. Wood fiber products are completely recyclable and can be disposed and collected at recovery centers.
- ▶ Some producers of insulation fiberboards collect used panels to be processed and reused in the same application.
- ▶ Among insulating materials made from renewable raw materials, wood fiber insulation boards are the most common, along with cellulose, hemp and flax short fibreboards.
- ▶ Wood fibreboards are known for their low volatile organic compound emission ratings. The improved indoor air quality improves public acceptability of these products.